

THE ROLE OF ONLINE PRESENTATION PLATFORMS IN MODERN EDUCATION

Ismoilova Sevinch Shavkatjon qizi

The 2nd year student at Navoi State University

supervisor: Phd. **Yugay Yevgeniya Viktorovna**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17636637>

Abstract: This study explores how online presentation platforms can make teaching and learning process more effective at university. It answers to the following questions: Are these tools beneficial for modern education? In what ways they can assist to teachers and learners? To answer these questions, the researcher has made a research based on advantages of presentation tools. Two groups of students attended to this research. At first, the lessons were taught in a traditional way and later online presentation tools such as Google Slides, Canva, Prezi and AhaSlides were used. After one month, students shared their opinions through a short poll. The results showed that most students found the lessons more interesting and easier to understand when online presentations were used. Overall, the study suggests that online presentation platforms can make lessons more engaging and creative.

Keywords: online presentations, university students, teaching effectiveness, engagement.

Introduction

In today`s world, online presentation platforms such as Google Slides Prezi, Canva, AhaSlides have become an integral part of modern education. They help teachers and students with creating and delivering knowledge in interactive, visual and accessible ways. They can also save time of educators and learners by encouraging them to be more attentive for lessons and their skills. According to Garrison and Vaughan (2017), the 21st – century classroom has evolved into ‘blended learning environment’, where online tools support collaboration and critical thinking. This pushes students forward to be more creative and innovative and makes them more aware of how to use digital platforms in life effectively. As well as countries have paid great attention to the digitalization of education. The Presidential Decree ‘On the Approval of the Digital Uzbekistan – 2030 Strategy’ emphasizes the importance of integrating modern technologies, online platforms and digital tools into all stages of the educational process to enhance teaching quality and accessibility (Presidential Decree No. PF-6079, 2020). Such reforms encourage teachers to integrate multimedia technologies into their lessons, thus aligning national education with global digital standards.

In what ways can online presentation platforms contribute to improving teaching and learning in modern education?

In this article, we will look through the appliance of certain online presentation platforms in teaching and the positive impact of them on academic outcomes. Multimedia presentations as Mayer (2021) defines, enhance retention and understanding through dual coding of visual and verbal information. This can also improves pedagogical effectiveness and learner motivation. Similarly, Sharipova (2024) emphasizes that digital platforms in Uzbekistan`s education system foster innovation and and inclusivity, providing students with modern communication skills. By this students could learn how to solve certain problems from different perspectives and could know their groupmates opinion.

According to Al-Munawwar and Hidayat (2020), online presentation tools promote students` active participation and help teachers diversify their instructional techniques. And in my opinion the ideas of all mentioned scientists have the same meaning.

Google Slides

Goggle Slides can contribute to improve teaching in several effective ways:

- teachers can make engaging slides with photos, videos and animations that make lessons more enjoyable and easier to understand;
- it is cloud-based and students can have access from any device anywhere with internet to review lessons;
- teacher can give regular feedback and comments on students` shared presentations to improve results.

Prezi

- it uses zooming interface which allows teachers to move smoothly with ideas and makes the process more engaging. Also students can easily understand the connections between concepts;
- visual style catches students` attention and keeps them motivated during the lesson;
- it allows students to work on the same presentation, so they can collaborate with each other.

Canva

- it helps design visually appealing presentations, slides and worksheets which makes materials attractive and easy to remember;
- its drag-and-drop interface and ready-made templates make it simple for everyone, even for beginners to create materials;
- teachers can also involve students in creating presentations and encourage them doing slides to boost active participation.

Aha Slides

- it allows educators to create live quizzes, polls and Q&A sessions to encourage active student participation;
- even shy and introvert students can share their opinions anonymously through polls that ensures that every student has their own perspectives;
- students can answer in real time, so teachers can see comments immediately and know which areas need improvement.

Research methodology

The sample of the study was chosen from 2nd course students at Navoi State University. The study was conducted among two groups of university students to evaluate the effectiveness of online presentation platforms in teaching. During the first phase, both groups attended lectures delivered through traditional methods and their preparation for practical lessons also followed conventional approaches. In the second phase, the professor introduced new topics using presentations created with online platforms such as Google Slides, Prezi and Canva. During practical classes, students accessed these materials on their own devices, participated in discussions and later began to present their own projects through similar platforms. To gather feedback, a poll was conducted via AhaSlides, asking students to reflect on their one-month experience of using online presentation tools in the learning process.

Questions

To know students` opinion about the use of online presentation platforms following statements are used:

1. I was familiar with online presentation platforms before this course
2. Online presentations helped me understand lecture materials more clearly.
3. Using online presentation platforms made me more active during classes.
4. The online presentation platforms were easy to access and use on my device.
5. I am satisfied with learning through online presentation platforms.

Results

After a month experience, the results were the following among two groups. A 100% system was used to get students` attitudes towards platforms:

Num ber	Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Stronly agree
1	I was familiar with online presentation platforms before this course	6%	10%	20%	40%	24%
2	Online presentations helped me understand lecture materials more clearly.	5%	7%	18%	42%	28%
3	Using online presentation platforms made me more active during classes	3%	10%	20%	40%	27%
4	The online presentation platforms were easy to access and use on my device.	2%	5%	15%	50%	28%
5	I am satisfied with learning through online presentation platforms.	4%	8%	17%	43%	28%

Discussion

The results of this research show that using online presentation platforms makes learning more active and interesting for students. Most of them agreed that these tools helped them understand lessons better and take part in classroom discussions. This supports the idea of Clark and Mayer (2021), who said that visual materials can improve attention and understanding in digital learning. Students also found the platforms straightforward to use and helpful for group work, which is similar to Reyna (2021), who emphasized that such tools enable students to share their opinions and learn together. Overall, the findings suggest that presentation platforms are an effective way to make lessons more modern and engaging

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research presented that online presentation platforms have a positive effect on both teaching and learning. Students became more active, confident and motivated during the lessons. Teachers could present new materials more clearly and easily, as well as make lessons more enjoyable. The use of online presentation tools also encouraged students to think creatively and study together. Therefore, using these platforms in university classes can help improve the quality of education make the learning process more interactive.

References:

1. Garrison, D. R., & Vaughan, N. D. (2017). *Blended Learning in Higher Education: Framework, Principles, and Guidelines*. Jossey-Bass.
2. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2020). Decree No. PF-6079: On the approval of the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy and measures for its effective implementation. Retrieved from <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/5031048>
3. Mayer, R. (2021). *Multimedia Learning* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
4. Sharipova, Y. K. (2024). Integrating New Generation Teaching Materials in English Language Education in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Foreign Languages in Uzbekistan*.
5. Al-Munawwar, S., & Hidayat, N. (2020). The Effect of Using Presentation Media on Students’ Learning Engagement. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 15(2), 45–53.
6. Clark, R. C., & Mayer, R. E. (2021). *E-Learning and the Science of Instruction* (4th ed.). Wiley.
7. Reyna, J. (2021). Using digital presentation tools to engage learners in higher education. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 37(5), 45–59.